

A TWO-STEP OPTIMIZATION SCHEME FOR GLOBAL OPTIMIZATION DESIGN OF COMPOSITE FRAME

Jingyuan Wang¹, Jun Yan¹, Zunyi Duan^{1,3,4}, Tao Yu¹, Erik Lund²

¹ State Key Laboratory of Structural Analysis for Industrial Equipment, Department of Engineering Mechanics, International Research Center for Computational Mechanics, Dalian University of Technology, Liaoning, Dalian, 116024, P. R. China

(yanjun@dlut.edu.cn)

² Department of Mechanical and Manufacturing Engineering, Aalborg University, DK-9220 Aalborg, Denmark

³ Harbin Electric Power Equipment Company Limited, Harbin Electric Corporation, 150028 Harbin, China

⁴ Department of Mechanical Engineering, Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology, 34141, Daejeon, Republic of Korea

Keywords: Composite frame, Equivalent stiffness, Global optimum, Fiber winding angle, Semi-analytical sensitivity analysis

ABSTRACT

Fiber-reinforced composite frame structure is considered to be an ideal material and structure for aerospace structure to realize ultra-lightweight and large-span demanding. Filament winding parameters (filament winding angle, winding thickness and winding layer order) have a significant effect on performance of the composite frame structure. However, when using the filament winding angle as design variables, the objective function feasible domains are non-convex and the traditional gradient-based optimization algorithm is not effective to get the global optimal solution. The present paper proposes a two-step optimization scheme for fiber-reinforced composites frame. When considering structural stiffness parameters (tension stiffness, bending stiffness, torsional stiffness) as the design variables, the optimization feasible domains are convex. Based on the derivation of equivalent stiffness of the composite beam with circular sections, the new method realizes the conversion of the design space from a non-convex domain to a convex domain. The proposed scheme can effectively solve the non-convex problem when the filament winding angles are considered as the design variables, which provides an effective method to obtain a global optimal solution in the optimization of composite frames. Numerical examples examine the computational efficiency of the proposed approach.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber-reinforced composite material has a complex microstructure such as filament winding angle, winding thickness and winding layer order. These characteristics provide designers large design space. Filament winding angle, winding thickness and winding layer order can be designed to improve the performance of the composite structure. When the filament winding parameters are considered as design variables, the design space of laminated composites is non-convex. Traditional optimization algorithms based on gradient information often converge to the local optima [1-4]. To overcome this problem, many researchers adopt heuristic optimization algorithms to optimize the composites [5-7]. However, such heuristic algorithms bring a large number of finite element analysis times in the optimization and spend lots of calculation time for complex structures. Sigmund [8] pointed out that it is unlikely for non-gradient topology algorithm to converge to a global optima even for extremely coarse finite element discretization.

An effective way to overcome the above challenges is to use lamination parameters as design variables in the laminated composite optimization design. Tsai and Pagano [9] firstly proposed the material invariants and 12 lamination parameters to describe stiffness property of the laminated composites. The inner surface of laminated composite materials, the outer surface and the coupling elastic tensor can be expressed as a linear combination of materials invariants and lamination

parameters. At this time each tensor contains four lamination parameters. Such using lamination parameters as the variables for the optimization of composite structure can significantly reduce the number of design variables. And the process of optimization do not need to consider the number of plies, stacking order, et al, reducing the difficulty of solving optimization. Miki [10] adopted the lamination parameters as an efficient parametrization of composite to render these optimization problems in a convex formulation and provided a new idea in the optimization of laminates. Grenestedt and Gudmundson [11] proved that when using lamination parameters as design variables, the feasible domains of the parameters is convex and the object functions to be maximized (stiffness, vibration frequencies, or buckling loads) are concave functions. It will significantly reduce the complexity for solving global optima of optimization problem. However, the 12 lamination parameters are not independent. Thus, the lamination parameters feasible domain boundaries must be given by analytical description and the lamination parameters can be corresponded to the real composite laminate ply design. Many researchers have studied the relation of lamination parameters feasible domain to filament winding parameters, see, e.g. Fukunaga and Sekine [12], Hammer and Bensøe [13], Diaconu et al. [14], Liu et al. [15], Setoodeh and Abdalla [16], Faria [17]. However, from the previous studies, the feasible region of lamination parameters currently known is limited to the part of the laminates which have a special ply order, or the structure with a relatively simple geometry. It greatly limits the application for optimization design of composite structure which adopting lamination parameters as the design variables. Therefore, Foldager et al. [1] proposed a jointed parameter method which combined the attributes of ply-angles and lamination parameters. The filament winding angle was used as design variables and lamination parameters are used to provide convexity.

Inspired by Foldager et al. [1], the paper adopt the jointed parameter method in the optimization design of composite frames and solve the problem of local optimal when using filament winding angle as design variables. The optimization model in filament winding angle space and structural stiffness parameters (tension stiffness, bending stiffness, torsional stiffness) space is established. The conversion of the optimization feasible region from a non-convex domain to a convex domain is realized. Numerical examples show that the proposed two-step optimization scheme can effectively avoid the local optima and serious dependence on initial value when using filament winding angles as the design variables.

2 EQUIVALENT THEORY TO COMPOSITE BEAM

To design efficient composite frame structures, effective computation of composite beam stiffness is necessary. Numerous laminated composite beam theories have been developed and evaluated e.g. Wild and Vickers [18], Vinson and Sierakowski [19], Jiang et al. [20], Xi and Chen [21]. The aim of this section is to obtain the equivalent stiffness of composite beam with circular section based on the layer-wise constant shear beam theory.

2.1 Layer-wise constant shear beam theory

For orthotropic composite single plate under the assumption of plane stress (x-y plane), the constitutive equation can be expressed as

$$\begin{pmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \sigma_{xy} \\ \sigma_{yz} \\ \sigma_{xz} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \bar{Q}_{11} & \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{16} & 0 & 0 \\ \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{22} & \bar{Q}_{26} & 0 & 0 \\ \bar{Q}_{16} & \bar{Q}_{26} & \bar{Q}_{66} & \bar{Q}_{44} & \bar{Q}_{45} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \bar{Q}_{44} & \bar{Q}_{45} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \bar{Q}_{45} & \bar{Q}_{55} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \\ \gamma_{yz} \\ \gamma_{xz} \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where \bar{Q}_{pq} is the transformed reduced stiffness.

To express concisely, laminated invariant parameters $U_1 - U_6$ are defined which can be expressed as Eq. (3).

$$\left. \begin{aligned} U_1 &= (3Q_{11} + 3Q_{22} + 2Q_{12} + 4Q_{66})/8 \\ U_2 &= (Q_{11} - Q_{22})/2 \\ U_3 &= (Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 2Q_{12} - 4Q_{66})/8 \\ U_4 &= (Q_{11} + Q_{22} + 6Q_{12} - 4Q_{66})/8 \\ U_5 &= (Q_{44} + Q_{55})/2 \\ U_6 &= (Q_{44} - Q_{55})/2 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2)$$

The Q_{pq} can be obtained by

$$\left. \begin{aligned} Q_{11} &= \frac{E_{11}}{1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}}, Q_{22} = \frac{E_{22}}{1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}}, Q_{12} = \frac{\nu_{21}E_{11}}{1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}} = \frac{\nu_{12}E_{11}}{1-\nu_{12}\nu_{21}} \\ Q_{44} &= G_{23}, Q_{55} = G_{31}, Q_{66} = G_{12} = G_{31} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (3)$$

Then the transformed reduced stiffness can be expressed as

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \bar{Q}_{11} \\ \bar{Q}_{22} \\ \bar{Q}_{12} \\ \bar{Q}_{44} \\ \bar{Q}_{55} \\ \bar{Q}_{45} \\ \bar{Q}_{66} \\ \bar{Q}_{16} \\ \bar{Q}_{26} \end{array} \right\} = \left[\begin{array}{cccccc} U_1 & U_2 & 0 & U_3 & 0 \\ U_1 & -U_2 & 0 & U_3 & 0 \\ U_4 & 0 & 0 & -U_3 & 0 \\ U_5 & U_6 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ U_5 & -U_6 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -U_6 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{1}{2}(U_1 - U_4) & 0 & 0 & -U_3 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2}U_2 & 0 & U_3 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2}U_2 & 0 & -U_3 \end{array} \right] \left\{ \begin{array}{l} 1 \\ \cos(2\theta_{i,j}) \\ \sin(2\theta_{i,j}) \\ \cos(4\theta_{i,j}) \\ \sin(4\theta_{i,j}) \end{array} \right\} \quad (4)$$

In the beam theory, it is generally accepted that $\sigma_y = \sigma_{yz} = \sigma_{xy} = 0$. Then we can obtain

$$\sigma_x = E_x^{i,j} \varepsilon_x \quad \sigma_{xz} = G_{xz}^{i,j} \gamma_{xz} \quad (5)$$

where $E_x^{i,j}$, $G_{xz}^{i,j}$ can be expressed as Eq. (6). $E_x^{i,j}$ is the equivalent elastic modulus of the i -th beam, j -th layer in x direction. $G_{xz}^{i,j}$ is the equivalent shear modulus of the i -th beam, j -th layer.

$$\left. \begin{aligned} E_x^{i,j} &= \bar{Q}_{11} + \bar{Q}_{12} \frac{(\bar{Q}_{16}\bar{Q}_{26} - \bar{Q}_{12}\bar{Q}_{66})}{(\bar{Q}_{22}\bar{Q}_{66} - \bar{Q}_{26}\bar{Q}_{26})} + \bar{Q}_{16} \frac{(\bar{Q}_{12}\bar{Q}_{26} - \bar{Q}_{16}\bar{Q}_{22})}{(\bar{Q}_{22}\bar{Q}_{66} - \bar{Q}_{26}\bar{Q}_{26})} \\ G_{xz}^{i,j} &= (\bar{Q}_{55} - \frac{\bar{Q}_{45}^2}{\bar{Q}_{44}}) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (6)$$

2.2 The equivalent stiffness of the composite beam with circular section

The composite beam with circular cross section is shown in Figure 1. The x direction is perpendicular to the y - z plane. R is the distance from the center to the neutral layer. h is the total cross-sectional thickness. ρ is the integration variable in the thickness. Based on the derivation of the single layer equivalent elastic modulus and shear modulus, for N layers laminated beams, the equivalent elastic modulus and shear modulus can be expressed as the integral along the cross-sectional thickness. Because of the different winding angles of each layer, the equivalent elastic modulus of single is non-continuous. Therefore, the integration in thickness direction is expressed in the form of accumulating layer by layer as Eq. (7). N^{lay} is the number of layers in a beam.

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of the composite beam with circle cross-section

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \overline{E}_x^i &= \int_{R-h/2}^{R+h/2} E_x^{i,j} d\rho = \sum_{j=1}^{N^{lay}} E_x^{i,j} \\ \overline{G}_{xz}^i &= \int_{R-h/2}^{R+h/2} G_{xz}^{i,j} d\rho = \sum_{j=1}^{N^{lay}} G_{xz}^{i,j} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (7)$$

To express the design variables in stiffness parameter space concisely, the equivalent elastic modulus \overline{E}_x^i and shear modulus \overline{G}_{xz}^i of the i -th beam are labeled as \overline{StiP}^i (**Stiffness Parameters**).

Therefore, for the composite beam with circle cross-section, the equivalent tensile stiffness \overline{EA}^i , bending stiffness \overline{EI}^i and torsional stiffness \overline{GIp}^i can be expressed as

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \overline{EA}^i &= \overline{E}_x^i A^i = \int_0^{2\pi} d\theta \int_{R-h/2}^{R+h/2} \rho E_x^{i,j} d\rho \\ \overline{EI}^i &= \overline{E}_x^i I^i = 1/2 \int_0^{2\pi} d\theta \int_{R-h/2}^{R+h/2} \rho^3 E_x^{i,j} d\rho \\ \overline{GIp}^i &= \overline{G}_{xz}^i Ip^i = \int_0^{2\pi} d\theta \int_{R-h/2}^{R+h/2} \rho^3 G_{xz}^{i,j} d\rho \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (8)$$

3 THE TWO-STEP OPTIMIZATION SCHEME

In traditional optimization algorithms based on gradient information, the optimization always converge to a local optima rather than the global optima for a non-convex objective function domain. To solve this problem, Foldager et al. [1] proposed a joint parametric approach that established a minimum optimization problem of laminated parameter space and achieved to find a new starting point for optimization in parameter space. This paper applies the joint parametric method to the optimization of fiber-reinforced composite frame. In the analysis of frame structure, the overall stiffness matrix and the element stiffness parameters (tension stiffness, bending stiffness and torsional stiffness) have a linear relationship. Thus the optimized feasible domains are convex when considering structural stiffness parameters as the design variables. Then the minimum optimization problem of structural stiffness parameter space is established and a new starting point for optimization in angle space is obtained. Through multiple iterations, the approximate global optimal solution can be obtained when considering filament winding angles as the variables in fact.

Figure 2 shows the optimization flowchart of the two-step scheme. The superscript SP and OPT denote the Starting Point and OPTimum respectively.

Figure 2: Optimization flowchart of the two-step scheme

In the paper, the optimization objective function is minimizing the structural compliance. Generally, the layer thickness is a fixed value in the design of the composite laminated frame structure, thus we only consider filament winding angles as design variables in this paper. $(\theta_{i,j})^k$ and $(\overline{StP}^i)^k$ is the filament winding angle and stiffness parameter of the k -th converting step, respectively. The schematic diagram of the two space optimization is shown in Figure 3 where x-axis is the angle and stiffness parameter space and y-axis is the value of the objective function. The solid black line represents the non-convex domain of objective function in angle space. Point A is a local optimum. Point E is the global optimum. The black dotted line represents the convex domain of the objective function in the stiffness parameter space. The solving process is divided into the following five steps as Foldager et al. [1] suggested.

Figure 3: Schematic diagram of the two-step optimization

- I. Initialize of angle space optimization and generate a set of random or specific initial filament winding angles $^{SP}\theta_{i,j}$ which are corresponding to the starting point O as shown in Figure 3.
- II. Adopt sequence quadratic program in angle space to find the local optimum point A and the filament winding angle $^{OPT}\theta_{i,j}$ by several iterations.
- III. Convert the filament winding angle $^{OPT}\theta_{i,j}$ corresponding to point A to the stiffness parameter space.

The local optimal stiffness parameter $(\overline{OPTStiP}^i)^k$ can be obtained by Eq. (8). Then calculate the objective sensitivity information with respect to stiffness parameters $\frac{\partial f}{\partial (\overline{OPTStiP}^i)^k}$ by semi-analysis method.

- IV. Based on the local optimal stiffness parameter $(\overline{OPTStiP}^i)^k$, the corresponding objective function point F can be found in the parameter space. Establish the new minimizing optimization problem with a double-objective function in the parameter space. Then determine the new starting point of the optimization problem $({}^{SP}\theta_{i,j})^{k+1}$. It is worth pointing out that the new starting point of optimization need to satisfy the following constraints:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} f\{({}^{SP}\theta_{i,j})^{k+1}\} &\leq f\{(\overline{OPT}\theta_{i,j})^k\} \\ ({}^{SP}\theta_{i,j})^{k+1} &\neq (\overline{OPT}\theta_{i,j})^k \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (9)$$

which guarantee the optimized direction toward a lower point in the objective function. Through the double-objective function, a new point G in stiffness space which is located below the point F can be obtained. The point G in the parameter space is corresponding to point D $({}^{SP}\theta_{i,j})^{k+1}$ in the angle space which is located between point B and C. The double objective minimize optimization problem $\min I$ will be illustrated in the next section.

- V. Using $({}^{SP}\theta_{i,j})^{k+1}$ in the angle space as a new starting point to optimize and get the point E. Repeat steps III, IV in this process until the Eq. (10) can not determine a new starting point for optimization. Thus f^E is the approximate global optimum for the optimization.

3.1 Determine the new starting point for optimization

As shown in Eq. (10), a double-objective minimizing optimization problem is proposed to determine the new starting point for optimization.

$$\min_{\theta_{i,j}} I = \{4f_1 + f_2\} \quad (10)$$

f_1 can be expressed as Eq. (11). The optimization of f_1 minimizes the distance between \overline{StiP}^i in the stiffness parameter space and the optimal stiffness parameter $\overline{StiP}^i(\theta_{i,j})$ obtained in the angle space. N^{tub} represents the number of beams of the structure.

$$f_1 = \sum_{i=1}^{N^{tub}} \left(1 - \frac{\overline{StiP}^i(\theta_{i,j})}{\overline{OPTStiP}^i} \right) \quad (11)$$

The purpose of f_2 is to ensure that the minimization problem in Eq. (10) can obtain a lower objective function value. f_2 can be expressed as follows:

$$f_2 = \sum_{i=1}^{N^{tub}} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} a_{11}\overline{StiP}^i(\theta_{i,j}) + b_{11} \left| \overline{StiP}^i(\theta_{i,j}) \leq \overline{OPTStiP}^i \right. \\ a_{12}\overline{StiP}^i(\theta_{i,j}) + b_{12} \left| \overline{StiP}^i(\theta_{i,j}) > \overline{OPTStiP}^i \right. \\ a_{21}\overline{StiP}^i(\theta_{i,j}) + b_{21} \left| \overline{StiP}^i(\theta_{i,j}) \leq \overline{OPTStiP}^i \right. \\ a_{22}\overline{StiP}^i(\theta_{i,j}) + b_{22} \left| \overline{StiP}^i(\theta_{i,j}) > \overline{OPTStiP}^i \right. \end{array} \left| \begin{array}{l} \frac{\partial f}{\partial \overline{OPTStiP}^i} \leq 0 \\ \frac{\partial f}{\partial \overline{OPTStiP}^i} > 0 \end{array} \right. \right\} \quad (12)$$

Parameters $a_{m,n}$ and $b_{m,n}$ can be obtained by following formulas:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} a_{11} &= \frac{0.8h_i}{\overline{OPTStiP}^i - 0.25h_i(1 - \overline{OPTStiP}^i) + 1}, & a_{21} &= \frac{-0.05h_i}{\overline{OPTStiP}^i - 0.25h_i(1 - \overline{OPTStiP}^i) + 1} \\ a_{12} &= \frac{0.05h_i}{\overline{OPTStiP}^i - 0.25h_i(1 - \overline{OPTStiP}^i) - 1}, & a_{22} &= \frac{-0.8h_i}{\overline{OPTStiP}^i - 0.25h_i(1 - \overline{OPTStiP}^i) - 1} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (13)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} b_{11} &= -h_i + a_{11} \quad , \quad b_{12} = -0.2h_i - a_{12} \\ b_{21} &= 0.2h_i + a_{21} \quad , \quad b_{22} = h_i - a_{22} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (14)$$

The variable h_i is the lamination parameter sensitivity normalized with respect to the numerically largest stiffness parameters sensitivity.

$$h_i = \frac{\partial f / \partial^{OPT} \overline{StiP}^i}{\left| \partial f / \partial^{OPT} \overline{StiP}^i \right|_{\max}} \quad (15)$$

More details about the selection and physical meaning of specific parameters please refer to reference [1].

4 OPTIMIZATION FORMULA AND SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS

Assume that each beam has the same winding layer thickness and the number of winding layers. The optimization formulas of composite frame in angle space are shown as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{find } \mathbf{X} &= \{\theta_{i,j}\} \\ \text{min } \mathbf{f} &= \mathbf{U}^T \mathbf{K} \mathbf{U} \\ \text{s. t. } \mathbf{K} \left(\mathcal{D}_n^e(\theta_{i,j}) \right) \mathbf{U} &= \mathbf{F} \\ \theta_{i,j} &\in [-90^\circ, 90^\circ] \\ i &= 1, 2, \dots, N^{tub}, j = 1, 2, \dots, N^{lay} \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

where the objective function f is the structural compliance. $\theta_{i,j}$ is the filament winding angle. The subscript i and j denote the i -th beam and j -th layer respectively.

In order to perform gradient-based optimization efficiently, the work adopts the semi-analytical method (SAM) (Lund [22]; Cheng and Olhoff [23]; Blasques and Stolpe [24]) which has highly computational efficiency and wide applications in the sensitivity analysis of finite element models. This section only gives sensitivity analysis method for the filament winding angle. And the sensitivity for the stiffness parameter $(\overline{StiP})^k$ can be obtained in the same way. The sensitivity of the objective function with respect to design variable $\theta_{i,j}$ is given as

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial \theta_{i,j}} = \sum_{n=1}^{N^{ele}} \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{U}_n^T}{\partial \theta_{i,j}} \mathbf{K}_n \mathbf{U}_n + \mathbf{U}_n^T \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{K}_n}{\partial \theta_{i,j}} \mathbf{U}_n + \mathbf{K}_n \frac{\partial \mathbf{U}_n}{\partial \theta_{i,j}} \right) \right) \quad (17)$$

where \mathbf{U}_n is the displacement vector of element n . \mathbf{K}_n is the corresponding element stiffness matrix of element n . Furthermore, making use of the equilibrium conditions $\mathbf{K}_n \mathbf{U}_n = \mathbf{F}$ and assuming design independent loads, Eq. (17) can be simplified as

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial \theta_{i,j}} = \sum_{n=1}^{N^{ele}} -\mathbf{U}_n^T \frac{\partial \mathbf{K}_n}{\partial \theta_{i,j}} \mathbf{U}_n \quad (18)$$

The sensitivities $\frac{\partial \mathbf{K}_n}{\partial \theta_{i,j}}$ is implemented as

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{K}_n(\theta_{i,j})}{\partial \theta_{i,j}} \approx \frac{\mathbf{K}_n((\theta_{i,j})+s \cdot \mathbf{e}_l) - \mathbf{K}_n(\theta_{i,j})}{s} \quad (19)$$

where s is the step size and \mathbf{e}_l is the unit vector of the l -th design variable and the step size s is set to 1×10^{-6} in this paper.

5 NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

In the paper we consider a spatial eight-beam frame structure, loading/boundary conditions and geometric sizes are shown in Figure 4. The beam 5, 7 are applied with a axial concentrate force respectively. Fiber material properties are shown in Table 1. Assume each composite beam has the same

number of layers $N^{lay} = 4$. Each layer has a fixed thickness $t_{tot}^i/N^{lay} = 0.1mm$. t_{tot}^i is the total layer thickness of the i -th composite beam.

Figure 4: Eight-beam spatial composites frame

E_{11}	143 GPa
$E_{22} = E_{33}$	10 GPa
G_{12}	6 GPa
G_{13}	5 GPa
G_{23}	3 GPa
ν_{12}	0.3
ν_{13}	0.2
ν_{23}	0.52
ρ	1800 kg/m ³

Table 1: Material properties of the uni-directional glass reinforced epoxy

Numerical examples are carried out in two different types of initial micro fiber angle: the uniform initial angle $\theta_{i,j} = 45^\circ$, $\theta_{i,j} = 60^\circ$ and the random initial angle. The optimization results for three kinds of micro fiber winging angles are shown in Table 2. Angles on the left are the winding angle of outer layers in Table 2. The iteration history of objective function is shown as Figure 5.

Beam number	Result with 45° initial angle/°	Result with 45° initial angle/°	Result with random initial angle/°
1	(-15.16/-5.34/0.56/0.57)	(-15.28/-4.66/-1.80/-1.70)	(-12.99/-4.80/-0.36/0.34)
2	(-14.13/-5.11/-0.91/0.90)	(13.82/-4.83/-1.37/-1.11)	(-14.64/-6.39/-1.58/-1.54)
3	(-15.16/-5.34/0.56/0.57)	(-13.43/-5.69/0.14/0.27)	(-12.88/-4.67/-0.10/-0.04)
4	(-14.13/-5.11/0.91/0.90)	(13.55/-6.40/-1.37/0.87)	(-12.53/-4.68/-0.23/-1.57)
5	(-0.81/-0.67/0.45/0.67)	(0.81/-0.41/-0.35/0.41)	(0.81/0.45/-0.29/-0.65)
6	(16.24/13.87/-0.55/0.51)	(17.67/11.65/-0.53/-0.49)	(-16.68/-12.07/0.60/-0.18)
7	(-0.81/-0.67/0.45/0.67)	(0.81/-0.40/0.49/0.43)	(0.79/-0.42/-0.47/-0.65)
8	(-13.54/-6.96/-1.05/-1.04)	(17.66/11.65/-0.53/-0.52)	(-16.74/-12.07/-0.21/-0.82)
Obj	20.712	20.732	20.731

Table 2: The optimization results of three kinds of initial fiber angle

Figure 5: Objective iteration history with three kinds of initial fiber winding angle

As shown in Figure 5, the minimized problem ($\min_{\theta_{i,j}} I = \{4f_1 + f_2\}$) is solved twice and once in stiffness parameter space respectively when adopting uniform and random initial initial angles. The conversion times are relevant to the distance between the global optimum and initial point in optimization problem which is shown in Figure 3. Thus for different initial angles, the frequency of solving the stiffness parameter space optimization problem is different. The objective function nearly converge to a same value in the end of the optimization.

As shown in Table 2, the values of objective function and optimal micro angle are very close in three examples with different initial angles. It is worth pointing out that a positive angle or a negative angle in a same value have the same contribution to the stiffness of the structure in this work. The concentrated loads are applied on the beams 5, 7 shown as figure 4. The whole structure have a torsional deformation and the beam 5, 7 mainly sustain axial tension. Winding angles in different layers have different effects on the structural stiffness. Observing the optimal winding angle, the outer fiber winding angle of beams 1-4 and 6, 7 have a relatively larger value than inner winding angles which are close to zero (along the axis of beams). The Larger outer winding angle is more favorable to resist shear force caused by the twisting. All the fiber winding angles of beam 5 and 7 are close to zero to improve the axial stiffness.

According to the optimization result and objective function iteration history as shown in Table 2 and Figure 5, the two-step method can obtain an approximate global optimal solution in composite frame structure optimization when using three kinds of initial fiber winding angle as design variable. The method effectively overcome the dependence on initial value in traditional gradient-based optimization algorithm.

To further verify the validity of the two-step optimization scheme, particle swarm optimization (PSO Particle swarm optimization) is adopted to solve the example. Table 3 shows the optimal result of the PSO method with 35 particles.

Beam number	Optimized fiber winding angle/ ^o
1	(-13.67/-5.80/-0.88/0.14)
2	(-13.94/-5.39/-0.85/-0.13)
3	(-14.03/-5.80/-0.86/-0.14)
4	(-13.88/-5.42/-0.80/-0.15)
5	(0.17/0.06/-0.06/-0.86)
6	(-17.15/-12.79/0.12/-0.00)
7	(0.04/-0.13/-0.00/-0.05)
8	(-17.22/-12.89/-0.02/-0.00)
Obj	20.708

Table 3: The optimization results of particle swarm optimization

The final objective function value in PSO method is 20.708. Comparing with the result in PSO, the optimal objective function value of two-step optimization scheme have the relative errors 0.019%, 0.12% and 0.11% for the three different initial angles, respectively. The result obtained by the two-step optimization scheme can be regarded as an approximate global optimal solution.

The optimal micro fiber winding angles shown in Table 3 are similar to those shown in Table 2. Although there is a little difference on the value of angle, the overall trend of the angle distribution is the same. The optimization results of two-step method and particle swarm algorithm reflects that the feasible region of optimization is multimodal and complex for composite material when considering fiber winding angle as design variables. Global optimal solution is surrounded by many similar local peak point. Despite some intelligent algorithms can obtain relatively credible global optimal solution, the computational efficiency of these intelligent algorithms is much lower than the two-step optimization method proposed in the paper.

6 CONCLUSION

A two-step optimization scheme to solve the problem of local optimal solution when using fiber winding angles as design variables is proposed. The equivalence stiffness of composite beam with circle cross-section is derived. A minimizing optimization problem in the structural stiffness parameter space is established and realizes the conversion of the design space from a non-convex domain to a convex domain. The validity of the two-step optimization scheme is verified by three cases which have different initial fiber winding angle. The optimal fiber winding angles are reasonable according to the load conditions. The optimized results are compared with the global optimal solution in PSO method. Numerical examples show that the proposed two-step optimization scheme can effectively avoid the local optimum difficulty with winding angles as the design variables and obtained the approximate global optimal solution.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Financial supports for this research were provided by the National Natural Science Foundation of China (No. 11372060, 11672057 and 11711530018), Program (LJQ2015026) for Excellent Talents at Colleges and Universities in Liaoning Province, the 111 project (B14013), and the Fundamental Research Funds for the Central Universities (DUT16ZD215). These supports are gratefully acknowledged.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Foldager, J.S. Hansen, N. Olhoff. 1998. A general approach forcing convexity of ply angle optimization in composite laminates. *Structural Optimization*, 16(2-3), 1998, pp. 201-211.
- [2] M. Bruyneel, C. Fleury. Composite structures optimization using sequential convex programming. *Advances in Engineering Software*, 33(7), 2002, pp. 697-711.
- [3] M. Bruyneel, P. Duysinx, C. Fleury. A family of MMA approximations for structural optimization. *Structural and Multidisciplinary Optimization*, 24(4), 2002, pp. 263-276.
- [4] R. Sørensen, J. Kann. Optimisation of Composite Structures Using Lamination Parameters in a Finite Element Application. Master's thesis, Department of Mechanical & Manufacturing Engineering, Aalborg University, 2011.
- [5] K.J. Callahan, G.E. Weeks. Optimum design of composite laminates using genetic algorithms. *Composites Engineering*, 2(3), 1992, pp. 149-160.
- [6] S. Deng, P.F. Pai, C.C. Lai. A solution to the stacking sequence of a composite laminate plate with constant thickness using simulated annealing algorithms. *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, 26(5-6), 2005, pp. 499-504.
- [7] N. Chang, W. Wang, W. Yang, J. Wang. Ply stacking sequence optimization of composite laminate by permutation discrete particle swarm optimization. *Structural and Multidisciplinary Optimization*, 41(2), 2009, pp. 179-187.

- [8] O. Sigmund. On the usefulness of non-gradient approaches in topology optimization. *Structural and Multidisciplinary Optimization*, 43(5), 2001, pp. 589-596.
- [9] S.W. Tsai, N.J. Pagano. Invariant properties of composite materials. No. AFML-TR-67-349. Air force materials lab wright-patterson afb ohio. 1968.
- [10] M. Miki. Material design of composite laminates with required in-plane elastic properties. *Proc Progress in Science and Engineering of Composites, ICCM IV, Tokyo*. 1982.
- [11] J.L. Grenestedt, P. Gudmundson. Layup optimization of composite-material structures. optimal design with advanced materials. *Optimal design with advanced materials*, 1993, pp. 311-336.
- [12] H. Fukunaga, H. Sekine. Stiffness design method of symmetrical laminates using lamination parameters. *Aiaa Journal*, 30(11), 1992, pp. 2791-2793.
- [13] V.B. Hammer, M.P. Bendsøe, R. Lipton. Parametrization in laminate design for optimal compliance. *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, 34(4), 1997, pp. 415-434.
- [14] C.G. Diaconu, M. Sato, H. Sekine. Buckling characteristics and layup optimization of long laminated composite cylindrical shells subjected to combined loads using lamination parameters. *Composite Structures*, 58(4), 2002, pp. 423-433.
- [15] S.T. Liu, Y.P. Hou, X. Sun, Y.C Zhang. A two-step optimization scheme for maximum stiffness design of laminated plates based on lamination parameters. *Composite Structures*, 94(12), 2012, pp. 3529-3537.
- [16] S. Setoodeh, M.M. Abdalla, Z. Gürdal. Design of variable-stiffness laminates using lamination parameters. *Composites Part B: Engineering*, 37(4-5), 2006, pp. 301-309.
- [17] A.R. Faria. Optimization of composite structures under multiple load cases using a discrete approach based on lamination parameters. *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering*, 104(9), 2015, pp. 827-843.
- [18] P.M. Wild, G.W. Vickers. Analysis of filament-wound cylindrical shells under combined centrifugal, pressure and axial loading. *Composites Part A Applied Science & Manufacturing*, 28(28), 1997, pp. 47-55.
- [19] J.R. Vinson, R.L. Sierakowski. *The behavior of structures composed of composite materials*. Springer Science & Business Media, 2012.
- [20] L.Z. Jiang, X.M. Wen, X.R. Ma, B.L. Wan. On the equivalent model of composite tubular element. *Engineering Mechanics*, 3:019, 2000.
- [21] Z. Xi, H. Chen. The theory for composite laminated beams. *Acta Materiae Compositae Sinica*, 11(2), 1994, pp. 1-6.
- [22] E. Lund. Finite element based design sensitivity analysis and optimization. Ph.D. Thesis. Institute of Mechanical Engineering, Aalborg University, Denmark. 1994.
- [23] G. Cheng, N. Olhoff. Rigid body motion test against error in semi-analytical sensitivity analysis. *Computers & Structures*, 46(3), 1993, pp. 515-527.
- [24] J.P. Blasques, M. Stolpe. Maximum stiffness and minimum weight optimization of laminated composite beams using continuous fiber angles. *Structural and Multidisciplinary Optimization*, 43(4), 2011, pp. 573-588.